

FELLOWSHIP

April 2025

Timarni: A Self-Sustaining Town City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories, concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Letter of Timarni to its Citizens

Dear Citizens,

I hope this letter finds you well. I am writing this letter to reflect on the 10 years of work that you would have done as a citizen.

Timarni achieved its dream of becoming a vibrant, self-reliant town rooted in agriculture, skill development, and sustainable industries. Leveraging its rich farming heritage, the town successfully established food processing units, dairy farms, and organic farming ventures, creating numerous jobs and reducing dependency on external markets. Cold storage facilities and efficient supply chains were built, significantly reducing post-harvest losses and increasing farmers' incomes. Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) and skill development centres were set up, equipping the youth with expertise in trades like mechanics, carpentry, and agro-based industries, keeping talent local and boosting employment opportunities.

The town also harnessed its natural resources to develop sustainable timber and wood-based industries, including furniture-making and handicrafts, fostering eco-friendly businesses and promoting local artisans. With strong government support and community collaboration, Timarni transformed into a regional hub for processed agricultural goods, skilled labour, and eco-friendly timber products. This holistic growth improved livelihoods, strengthened the local economy, and positioned Timarni as a model of sustainable development and innovation. I would like to thank you for making me capable of achieving my dream as a city, which was only possible by the effort you have putted with heart in making me “A place to live with peace.”

Your Town,
Timarni, M.P.

Timarni: A Self-Sustaining Town

Timarni moves with the rhythm of its people—farmers tending to their fields, shopkeepers opening their stores, students heading to school, and workers going about their daily tasks. Life here follows a predictable pattern, a sense of familiarity woven into each day. The morning begins with the hum of activity as motorcycles glide through the streets, children rush to their schools, and shopkeepers prepare for the day's customers. Municipal workers begin their work, cleaning the town to ensure its waste management and beautification.

For many, this routine offers comfort. Yet, for others, predictability brings a sense of monotony. Rajesh Verma, a shopkeeper, reflects, *“Since our schedules are fixed, we see the same people every day, making life a little uninteresting.”*

For those who grew up in Timarni, the town holds memories of simpler times—school days spent at Nagar Palika School, evenings wandering the gullies of New Market, and the excitement of attending karate classes under a government-funded program. The railway station serves as more than just a transit point; it is a place of belonging, where familiar faces cross paths daily during morning walks. Even as Timarni expands and modernizes, it remains deeply tied to its traditions, cultural spaces, and childhood nostalgia. Sunita Sharma, a retired teacher, fondly shares, *“There is a spot in the town called Rain Basera which gives life to the town. People come there to talk and enjoy their evening time together.”*

The heart of Timarni beats strongest in its shared experiences, its festivals, and its public spaces. The Old Shankar Mandir, over two hundred years old, remains a hub of religious and social gatherings. Festivals like Navratri and Ramlila bring together people from surrounding areas, while the Kanha Baba ka Mela reminds many of their childhood—siblings piling into bullock carts, eager for a day of celebration.

The town's historical roots run deep, from the Rajabarari Hills' folk culture to the Gadi (Marathon ka Quila), a structure that stands as a testament to the past. *“One thing that makes the culture of Timarni different is the fact that there is respect among the population despite economic differences,”* remarks Ramesh Yadav, a local historian.

 “There is no bus stand here. The children stand on the road waiting for the bus. This needs to change,”
Anil Kumar, a daily commuter.

Yet, beneath the charm of its familiarity, the town faces significant challenges. Students struggle with a lack of higher education institutions, sports facilities, and libraries, leaving them with limited opportunities to expand their knowledge without traveling outside the town.

Healthcare is another pressing concern. The town's hospital lacks basic facilities, forcing residents to travel long distances for even minor medical needs. Meena Devi, a homemaker, worries, *“Regarding health, the hospital should be better. We should have all necessary facilities so that people don't have to leave town for basic treatments.”* The railway station is in dire need of improvements, and public transport infrastructure remains inadequate, with no proper bus stand, leaving children and workers standing on the roads, waiting for transportation.

Infrastructure concerns are further aggravated by frequent flooding, even though the town does not have a major river. Poor drainage, caused by increasing concrete buildup over natural water channels, has led to worsening conditions each year. Environmentalist Vinod Jain highlights, *“Despite there being no major river, flooding is a common problem due to the bad drainage system. People have built over the natural water channels, making the problem worse day by day.”*

The frustration of the residents is not just about the lack of infrastructure but also about the disconnect between policymakers and the people. Decisions like the relocation of the mandi to Dholpur are made without considering the economic impact on local businesses. Modernization is creeping in, bringing environmental concerns such as rising air pollution and reckless use of natural resources.

Yet, hope persists in the collective dreams of the people. There is a shared vision of a Timarni that offers opportunities for its youth, better education, and a thriving sports culture. The allocation of land for playgrounds and recreational spaces is eagerly awaited. The town also envisions economic growth through local industries that utilize its rich agricultural resources. *“We should have industries based on local raw materials to boost the economy and create jobs for future generations,”* suggests Manoj Tripathi, a local entrepreneur.

Public participation in governance is another key demand. Many believe that environmental sustainability must be prioritized, with a stronger focus on preserving green spaces and addressing climate-related issues. Advocate Shalini Pandey emphasizes, *“There is a major gap between policymakers and people. Public participation in decision-making should be ensured so that policies actually reflect the needs of the town.”*

Timarni’s dreams are deeply rooted in community well-being, respect for its cultural heritage, and aspirations for a better future. *“Everything is peaceful here, but it can be better with more opportunities for our youth and better urban planning,”* says retired school principal, Rajendra Tiwari.

Timarni is a town with a soul—a place where tradition and modern aspirations coexist. Its people do not seek to erase its past but to build upon it, ensuring that the town evolves while keeping its essence alive. As residents continue their daily routines, they do so with the hope that their voices will be heard, that the town’s strengths will be preserved, and that its future will be shaped by those who call it home.

History of Timarni

Timarni, a town with deep historical and cultural roots, has several landmarks and traditions that reflect its rich past. One of the most significant historical sites is the Old Lord Shiva temple, which has stood for more than a century. This temple is not just a place of worship but also a center for major religious gatherings and events. Over the years, it has remained a symbol of Timarni’s heritage, bringing people together for prayers and celebrations. The temple plays a crucial role in preserving the town's religious customs and is an important part of its identity.

Another key historical structure in Timarni is the small fortress known as "Gadi" that was Marathon ka Quila. This fort serves as a reminder of the town’s past and has historical significance attached to it. It is currently occupied by the Bhuskutha Parivar but the structure itself continues to evoke memories of the town’s history. While not widely known outside the region, the fort stands as a testimony to the historical events and rulers that once influenced Timarni.

Figure 1: Timeline of Historical Events in Timarni
Source: Author

History of Timarni

Apart from these historical landmarks, Timarni has a rich folk culture, particularly associated with the Rajabarari Hills. The folk songs and traditions of this region have been passed down through generations, preserving the unique cultural identity of the town. The area is also known for its diverse wildlife, which has been an integral part of its natural and historical landscape.

Timarni is known for its grand cultural celebrations, especially Navratri and Ramlila. The Navratri festival is celebrated with great enthusiasm, attracting people from neighboring towns who come to witness the grand festivities, traditional performances, and religious ceremonies. Similarly, the Ramlila of Timarni is one of the oldest in the region, deeply embedded in the town's cultural fabric. These festivals not only bring the community together but also serve as a means of preserving and passing down traditional rituals and practices.

Over the years, some historical and cultural sites in Timarni have changed. For instance, Timran River Ghat, once a place where people spent significant time with friends and family, has undergone changes, with certain parts being dismantled. However, despite these changes, some historical locations, such as the Shankar Mandir, continue to hold great importance. This temple, visited frequently by the locals, especially in the evenings, serves as a historical and spiritual retreat for many.

The Nehru Park, though not an ancient structure, has long been an important gathering space for the residents of Timarni. It represents the town's communal spirit and has been a place of social interaction for generations.

Timarni's historical and cultural uniqueness is also reflected in the respect and harmony among its people, regardless of their economic differences. This social fabric has remained intact over the years, making the town a place of strong cultural bonds and shared traditions.

Figure 2: The Old Shiv Temple
Source: Author

Figure 3: Gadi of Timarni-Main Gate
Source: Author

Everyday Life

Highly Satisfied & Happy

Majority of citizens find happiness to live in this small town and fulfill their daily routines, often due to their connection with nature, social interactions, or meaningful work. Farmers, for instance, wake up early and head straight to their fields, spending the entire day working with the land. For them, being surrounded by crops and open skies is a source of peace, and they don't feel the need for additional leisure time. The physical activity and the satisfaction of seeing their produce grow bring them a sense of accomplishment.

Others who are highly satisfied include people who incorporate morning walks and social gatherings into their day. Many start their mornings by walking near the railway station or in Nehru Park, where they interact with familiar faces and enjoy the fresh air.

These moments allow them to break the monotony of work and keep them physically and mentally active. Women in the town also find happiness in their routines, as they meet their friends in parks or temples in the evening, engaging in conversations that strengthen their social bonds. Teachers and educators also fall into this category.

Those who spend their day guiding students, managing educational institutes, and contributing to youth development find a strong sense of purpose. They believe that shaping young minds is rewarding and brings them immense satisfaction. Some people in the town cherish their spiritual connection with places like the temples along the Narmada River, where they go to find peace, especially in summer, or prefer being around wheat fields during winter. The natural surroundings, fresh air, and calm environment of these locations help them feel rejuvenated and content.

Figure 4: Rain Basera, Timarni
Source: Author

Figure 5: Picture from online interview
Source: Author

Moderately Satisfied

This group consists of people who have a structured and somewhat fulfilling routine but feels a lack of excitement or deep happiness. Shopkeepers and business owners fall into this category, as they follow a set schedule—opening their shops in the morning, attending to customers throughout the day, taking meal breaks, and closing at night.

While their work provides financial stability and keeps them engaged, it doesn't necessarily bring them joy or variety. Their interactions with customers and the community add social aspects to their routine, but the predictability of their work might limit their sense of fulfillment.

Similarly, government officials and revenue collectors play an essential role in the town's administration. Their day typically starts with reviewing revenue documents, tracking tax payments, and collecting fees. The income generated from their work contributes to the beautification of the town, road maintenance, and other development projects, giving them a sense of purpose. However, their daily tasks remain repetitive, and their interaction with people is often limited to financial transactions, making their routine more functional than enjoyable.

Students in Timarni also experience a structured but somewhat monotonous lifestyle. A significant portion of their day is spent in school, followed by evening activities such as karate classes. Some students find joy in wandering around town in places like Surya Tower and the New Market, while others feel restricted by their daily academic responsibilities.

Since karate classes in Timarni were government-supported but run by private teachers, they provided an interesting outlet for some students, adding a unique aspect to their day. However, for many, the overall routine remains predictable, with little variation outside of school and studies.

Less Satisfied & Disinterested

A segment of the population in Timarni finds their daily routine dull, repetitive, or uninspiring. Office workers and individuals involved in administrative jobs often experience this feeling. Their daily routine involves going to work, interacting with the same set of people, handling documents, and returning home, which makes their life feel unchanging. While their work is necessary for the functioning of the town, they do not derive personal satisfaction from it.

Another factor contributing to dissatisfaction is the lack of variety in social interactions. Since Timarni is a small town, the community is closely knit, and people interact with the same individuals daily. Many working-class individuals have fixed schedules, greeting the same people every day while commuting or working. This repetitive pattern creates a sense of monotony, making life feel less exciting over time.

Some individuals also express frustration over the lack of leisure activities. Unlike larger cities, Timarni does not offer many recreational spaces, sports facilities, or entertainment options. This makes it difficult for people, especially the youth, to break free from their routine and engage in new experiences. One person mentioned that they don't even feel the need for leisure time because their work involves enough physical movement, which suggests that they view their routine as more of a necessity than a fulfilling experience.

Places of Belonging

Figure 6: Landmarks of Timarni Town
Source: Author

Category (Group of People)	Places (Before)	Places (Now)
Religious & Historical Landmarks (Old Citizens, Devotees, Historians)	Old Lord Shiva Temple: A central place for religious programs and history.	Still a religious and cultural hub for the community.
Religious & Historical Landmarks (Old Citizens, Devotees, Historians)	Marathon ka Quila: A historic fort symbolizing the town's past.	Now occupied by the 'Bhuskutha Parivar.'
Religious & Historical Landmarks (Old Citizens, Devotees, Historians)	Shankar Mandir: A frequently visited historic temple.	Still holds significance but has undergone some changes.
Religious & Historical Landmarks (Old Citizens, Devotees, Historians)	Jain Temples (Basti Area): Associated with Acharya Rajneesh (Osho).	Still religiously significant but not as frequently visited.
Cultural & Social Spaces (All Generations - Youth, Families, Old Citizens)	Kanha Ka Mela: A fair visited with family on bullock carts.	Still organized, but fewer personal visits due to time constraints.
Cultural & Social Spaces (All Generations - Youth, Families, Old Citizens)	Ramlila of Timarni: One of the oldest in the region, attracting large audiences.	Continues to be celebrated with great enthusiasm.
Cultural & Social Spaces (All Generations - Youth, Families, Old Citizens)	Navratri Festival: A huge celebration drawing people from surrounding towns.	Still a grand event, maintaining its cultural significance.

Category (Group of People)	Places (Before)	Places (Now)
Cultural & Social Spaces (All Generations – Youth, Families, Old Citizens)	Folk Culture & Songs (Rajavari Hills): Traditional music and storytelling.	Still exists, but interest among the younger generation is declining.
Community & Gathering Places (Youth, Families, Social Groups)	Nehru Park: A central gathering space for residents.	Still a popular place for social interaction.
Community & Gathering Places (Youth, Families, Social Groups)	Rain Basera: A lively spot where people meet in the evenings. Musafirkhana (Railway Station): A familiar place for travelers and locals.	Still a vibrant meeting place for social interactions. Still in use, but the surroundings have changed.
Community & Gathering Places (Youth, Families, Social Groups)	Timran River Ghat: A place to spend time with friends and family.	Has changed significantly, with some parts dismantled.
Personal & Childhood Memories (Old Citizens, Youth, Former Residents)	Gujjar Hostel: Connected to childhood memories, volleyball games, and family history.	No longer the same, as childhood connections have faded.
Personal & Childhood Memories (Old Citizens, Youth, Former Residents)	Nagar Palika School: The primary place of education and strong childhood memories.	Has changed a lot over time, with a different environment now.
Personal & Childhood Memories (Old Citizens, Youth, Former Residents)	Badminton Ground (Colony): Created and used by friends for games.	Has changed to built up
Personal & Childhood Memories (Old Citizens, Youth, Former Residents)	Gujjar Hostel: Connected to childhood memories, volleyball games, and family history.	No longer the same, as childhood connections have faded.

Figure 7
Source: Author

Voices of Concern

Legend

- Municipal Boundary
- Important Landmark
- Node Points
- Recreational
- Water Body
- Connectivity**
- <all other values>
- type**
- Bridge
- Major rd
- NH12
- NH47
- NH59A
- other rd
- rail

Concern Areas in the Town Timarni

The voices of Timarni's citizens echo their concerns about the town's pressing issues, from inadequate infrastructure to environmental degradation.

The lack of higher education institutions and sports facilities limits opportunities for the youth, as Rohit Mishra laments, *"There are no good study or research institutes. For higher education, we don't have access to quality material, and we often have to leave the town."*

Healthcare is another major challenge, with residents forced to travel for basic medical care. Meena Devi expresses her worries, *"The hospital should be better. We should have all necessary facilities so that people don't have to leave town for basic treatments."*

Additionally, poor drainage systems cause frequent flooding, as environmentalist Vinod Jain warns, *"Despite there being no major river, flooding is a common problem due to the bad drainage system."*

The people of Timarni aspire for better urban planning, economic opportunities, and stronger governance, as Shalini Pandey emphasizes, *"Public participation in decision-making should be ensured so that policies actually reflect the needs of the town."*

"There are no good study or research institutes. For higher education, we don't have access to quality material, and we often have to leave the town."

- Rohit Mishra

Sports & Recreational Facilities

Timarni has a rich history of sports and physical activities, but the town lacks proper sports infrastructure for budding athletes. There is no dedicated sports complex or playground where children and young players can regularly practice. A ground exists for occasional tournaments, but it is not suitable for daily training. Many sports enthusiasts, especially those interested in kabaddi, karate, and badminton, find it difficult to pursue their passion due to the absence of proper coaching centers and practice areas.

The delay in sports infrastructure development has frustrated many residents, particularly as land for a sports facility has already been allocated but remains unused due to political tensions. Young players are forced to travel long distances to cities with better facilities, making it challenging to balance sports with academic commitments.

If sports infrastructure is improved, Timarni could host district-level or state-level tournaments, which would not only encourage young athletes but also bring economic and social benefits to the town.

Figure 8: Location of Annexation Sports Area
Source: Author

Figure 9: Zoomed in Image of the Playgrounds
Source: Author

Education & Research Facilities

One of the primary concerns in Timarni is the lack of quality education and research facilities, especially for higher education students. While primary and secondary schools exist, they often lack advanced study material, research opportunities, and specialized courses that could help students compete at a national level.

Without access to well-equipped libraries, laboratories, or research centers, students have to rely on external sources, often traveling to bigger cities for further education. This consumes their free time, as many students who leave Timarni for education use to return late due to better opportunities elsewhere.

If a well-structured higher education institution or public library were established, it would greatly benefit students. A library with access to modern technology, digital resources, and a quiet space for study and research would help bridge the existing knowledge gap.

Additionally, vocational training centers could provide practical skills for students who do not wish to pursue conventional academic degrees but still want career-oriented education in fields like agriculture, technology, and business.

Figure 10: Dayalbagh Educational Institute
Source: Author

Drainage & Flooding Issues

Despite not having a major river, flooding and waterlogging are recurring problems in Timarni, particularly during the monsoon season. This is primarily due to an inefficient drainage system, which has worsened over the years. Many natural drainage channels have been obstructed by unplanned concrete construction, leading to severe water accumulation in residential colonies during heavy rains.

The problem is further aggravated by poor waste management, as clogged drains and lack of proper sewage disposal contribute to stagnant water and related health hazards. If this issue is not addressed, it could lead to long-term infrastructural damage, property loss, and an increase in waterborne diseases. The municipality must take immediate action by investing in proper drainage systems, conducting regular maintenance, and implementing strict regulations against illegal construction blocking water flow.

Public Participation & Governance

One of the fundamental issues in Timarni is the lack of public participation in governance and policy-making. Many decisions regarding town planning, infrastructure, and resource allocation are made without proper consultation with the local population. As a result, there is a disconnect between what is planned on paper and what the citizens actually need.

For example, the allocation of land for a playground is still on hold despite numerous requests from the community. Similarly, essential projects such as hospital upgradation, bus stand construction, and sports facility development are either delayed or neglected due to bureaucratic inefficiencies and lack of public pressure. If people's perspectives and feedback were considered more actively, governance in Timarni would be more transparent and effective. Public forums, citizen committees, and regular town meetings could help bridge the gap between authorities and residents.

Economic & Business Concerns

Timarni has long depended on agriculture and small-scale businesses, but economic concerns have been growing in recent years. One major issue is the relocation of the local mandi to Dholpur, which threatens to reduce commercial activity in Timarni. The mandi is a crucial part of the town's economy, providing a marketplace for farmers, traders, and local businesses. Its shifting could negatively impact sales, transport costs, and employment opportunities in Timarni.

Additionally, the town lacks industrial growth despite having access to local raw materials that could support manufacturing and cottage industries. If small-scale industries, particularly those related to agriculture, handicrafts, or food processing, were established, it would generate employment for local youth and reduce migration to bigger cities. Encouraging entrepreneurship and business-friendly policies could help Timarni become economically self-sufficient and less dependent on external markets.

Cultural & Environmental Concerns

Timarni is witnessing rapid urbanization, but at the cost of losing its cultural essence and environmental stability. The town has a deep-rooted history, with festivals like Navratri and Ramlila, as well as folk traditions that are slowly fading due to modern influences. While development is necessary, it should not come at the expense of Timarni's unique cultural identity.

Additionally, environmental concerns are growing as rapid urbanization leads to reckless use of water resources, pollution, and deforestation. A particularly alarming issue is the cutting of trees under the pretext of beautification, which is negatively impacting the town's natural environment. Green spaces are shrinking, and air quality is gradually deteriorating. Sustainable urban planning is essential to maintain a balance between development and environmental conservation. Encouraging tree plantations, sustainable water management, and pollution control measures can help Timarni develop without compromising its natural beauty.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Potential Areas for the Town Timarni

Agro-Based Industry

Timarni has a strong agricultural foundation, and developing agro-based industries could significantly boost the local economy. With a large number of farmers engaged in crop production, setting up food processing units, dairy farms, and organic farming enterprises would create employment opportunities and reduce dependency on external markets. By utilizing locally available raw materials like wheat, soybeans, and pulses, the town can develop flour mills, oil extraction plants, and packaged food businesses.

Additionally, cold storage facilities and efficient supply chain management can help reduce post-harvest losses and increase farmers' profits. Encouraging cooperative farming models and farmer-producer organizations (FPOs) will ensure that small farmers can compete in larger markets. If proper government policies and investment in agro-industries are introduced, Timarni could become a hub for processed agricultural goods, improving both local livelihoods and regional trade.

Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) & Skill Development Centers

One of the biggest concerns in Timarni is the lack of higher education and technical training institutes. Establishing Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) and vocational centers would equip the youth with practical skills in fields like mechanical work, electrical engineering, welding, carpentry, plumbing, and computer applications. These skill-based courses would help students secure better job opportunities locally as well as in other cities.

Additionally, Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) could offer specialized training in agro-based industries such as food processing, packaging, and farm machinery operations. Encouraging collaborations with government schemes, private companies, and industry experts would provide students with hands-on learning experiences and enhance their employability. If such institutions are developed in Timarni, it would reduce migration of young talent to urban areas, keeping the workforce engaged and productive within the town itself.

Timber Production & Wood-Based Industries

Timarni's geographical location and natural resources make it an ideal place for developing timber-based industries. By promoting sustainable forestry and plantation programs, the town could develop sawmills, furniture-making units, and paper manufacturing plants. This would create a new economic sector while ensuring environmental sustainability through responsible logging practices.

Also, training in wood carving, furniture design, and bamboo craftsmanship could help establish small-scale businesses and promote local artisans. Timarni could develop as a centre for eco-friendly timber products, exporting handcrafted furniture, wooden toys, and decorative items to different parts of India. Government support in terms of subsidies, training, and market linkages would be crucial in making timber production a sustainable and profitable industry for the town's future.

*Vision for my town in the next 10 years will be to develop Timarni as a **planned settlement** for future population, keeping focus on Agriculture(in terms of production), Poultry, Commercial and Mandi (Warehouse). As per the growth rate Timarni population will be around 45,000 in next 10 years which will boost the commercial and education sector. To expand built up areas in such a manner which is **environmentally sustainable**. Another vision will be to solve planning problems in the city such as flooding, minimizing the probability of accidents at “Radhabai ki Puliya” over Timaran River.*

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Devesh Patwari

Devesh hails from a small town, Timarni in Madhya Pradesh. He is an ambitious planning student pursuing Bachelor of Planning from Department of Planning at the School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi. He has a keen desire to know about how towns function and contribute to their improvement. He has the ability to gather and analyze data with his knowledge in research methods, data collection techniques, and data analysis tools. He believes his academic experience can contribute to solve the urban issues and to give proposal for planned elements for my town. He remains eager to learn more and gain practical experience.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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